

Complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) with 5-Nitro-Resacetophenone Oxime

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The bis-complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) with 5-nitro-resacetophenone oxime have been prepared and characterized by magnetic measurements, spectral studies and X-ray powder patterns. The diamagnetic planar Ni(II) complex picks up two molecules of pyridine to form an octahedral adduct. X-ray powder patterns show that the Cu(II) complex is not isostructural with the Ni(II) complex.

5-NITRO-resacetophenone oxime (5-Nitro-rapox) reacts with transition metal ions to form coloured compounds. The structures of these metal complexes are of special interest because the coordinated ligand has a number of donor groups which can provide alternative sites for bonding. In the present investigation the complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) with 5-nitro-rapox have been prepared and characterized by magnetic measurements at low temperature, spectral studies and X-ray powder patterns.

Experimental

Chemicals and solvents used were of A.R. quality. 5-Nitro-rapox was prepared by the method reported in the literature^{1a, 1b}.

Preparation of bis-Cu(II) complex: To a solution of 1.1 g. of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 500 ml. of water was added slowly with stirring 2 g. of 5-nitro-rapox in 200 ml. of dioxane. The yellowish-green precipitate was digested on a hot water bath for 30 mins, filtered, washed with 500 ml. of hot water and then with 50 ml of absolute alcohol. The complex was dried at 100°. It could be prepared by adjusting the pH of the mixture to 2.5-6.9.

Preparation of bis-Ni(II) complex: A solution of 2 g. of 5-nitro-rapox in 200 ml of dioxane was added slowly with stirring to 0.912 g of $\text{NiSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ in 400 ml of water. The pH of the mixture was raised to 4.0-6.9 with 0.1N NaOH. The precipitate was digested on a hot water bath for 30 min. It was filtered, washed with 500 ml of hot water and 50 ml of absolute alcohol, and then dried at 100°.

Preparation of pyridine adduct of bis-Ni(II) complex: 2 g of Ni $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ were dissolved in minimum volume of pyridine. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was allowed to evaporate at room temperature. The solid was collected, air dried and analysed.

The magnetic susceptibility and spectral measurements were taken as reported elsewhere^{2a, 2b}. X-ray

powder diffraction patterns of complexes were taken with Guinier Camera of radius 114 mm with Fe-K α radiation.

Results and Discussion

The results of chemical analysis in Table I suggest that the green Ni(II) and yellowish-green Cu(II) complexes of 5-nitro-rapox may be represented as $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ respectively. Both the complexes are insoluble in water, dilute mineral acids and common organic solvents such as benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, carbon tetrachloride, etc., indicating that they are probably polymeric in nature. The bis-complexes of Ni(II) and Cu(II) dissolve in alkali to form orange-red solutions. They are stable up to 200°. Because of

TABLE I—CHEMICAL ANALYSIS OF Ni(II) AND Cu(II) COMPLEXES OF 5-NITRO-RAPOX AND THE PYRIDINE ADDUCT OF Ni(II) COMPLEX

Element	%Metal	%N	%C	%H
Found	12.3	11.8	40.3	3.20
Required for $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$	12.2	11.7	40.0	2.91
Found	13.0	11.8	40.0	3.00
Required for $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$	13.1	11.5	39.6	2.88
Found	9.10	13.0	48.6	3.50
Required for $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$	9.19	13.1	48.9	3.75

their insolubility in water and common organic solvents, their molecular weights could not be determined.

The diamagnetism of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ suggests that it is probably square-planar in structure involving dsp^2 hybridization. It dissolves in pyridine to form an adduct of the composition $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ (Py = pyridine), which is paramagnetic. Ni $(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2 \cdot 2\text{Py}$ obeys the Curie-Weiss law over the temperature range 83.5°-300°K with Weiss constant

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$\theta = 12^\circ\text{K}$. The magnetic moment of 2.85 ± 0.09 B.M., which is independent of temperature in the range $83.5^\circ\text{--}233.5^\circ\text{K}$, corresponds to two unpaired electrons. This leads to the conclusion that the diamagnetic square planar $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ picks up two molecules of pyridine to form an octahedral adduct. $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ is found to be paramagnetic and the magnetic moment (1.80 B.M.) corresponds very close to spin only value for one unpaired electron. It obeys the Currie-Weiss law in the temperature range of $83.5^\circ\text{--}300^\circ\text{K}$ with Weiss constant $\theta = +3^\circ\text{K}$.

The absorption spectra of 5-nitro-rapox, $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ were measured in NaOH solution. The $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions appear as strong peaks at 45.45 kK ($\epsilon = 7958$), 37.04 kK ($\epsilon = 12610$) and 25 kK ($\epsilon = 9649$) in 5-nitro-rapox and at 45.45 kK ($\epsilon = 24950$), 34.20 kK ($\epsilon = 27530$) and 2439 kK ($\epsilon = 24200$) in $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$, while they are observed as broad maxima at $35.71\text{--}33.33$ kK ($\epsilon = 76320$) and a strong peak at 24.39 kK ($\epsilon = 50300$) in $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$. The peak at 24.39 kK may have some contribution from charge transfer transition. The shoulder near 28.57 kK in Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes may be due to a charge transfer band.

The spectrum of sodium hydroxide solution of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ in the region $13.89\text{--}7.271$ kK reveals a broad maxima at $10.64\text{--}10.20$ kK ($\epsilon = 8.794$) which may be attributed to d-d transition in an octahedral Ni(II) complex. It may, therefore, be inferred that the planar $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ changes to an octahedral configuration in sodium hydroxide solution. This is supported by the fact that the magnetic moment of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ in NaOH solution is 3.2 B.M. at 301°K , as expected for octahedral environment around Ni(II). $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ in NaOH solution shows a shoulder near 11.63 kK ($\epsilon = 2.46$) in the region $7.407\text{--}12.82$ kK. The intensity of this band suggests that it may be assigned to d-d transition.

The reflectance spectra of $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ show a maximum at $17.24\text{--}17.54$ kK and a shoulder near 19.60 kK respectively. These bands may be attributed to d-d transition.

The assignments of infrared bands of 5-nitro-rapox, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ have been made on the basis of the bands reported in compounds of known structures and by comparing the bands in 5-nitro-rapox, its metal complexes, deuterated 5-nitro-rapox, resacetophenone, resacetophenone oxime and 5-nitro-resacetophenone.

The peaks at 3400 cm^{-1} and 3175 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox may be assigned to hydrogen bonded OH stretching vibrations. The extent of displacement from the position of the free OH group and the intensity of the bands indicate that intermolecular hydrogen bonding and chelation are present. The appearance of new bands near 2439 cm^{-1} and 2326 cm^{-1} in the deuterated 5-nitro-rapox provide evidence in support of the assignment. The OH stretching frequencies in $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ occur at 3400 cm^{-1} and 3060 cm^{-1} , while those in $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ are observed at 3440 cm^{-1} , 3220 cm^{-1} and 3100 cm^{-1} .

The infrared spectra of 5-nitro-rapox and its metal complexes in the region 1700 to 1000 cm^{-1} are very complicated and so it is difficult to assign the bands in this region without ambiguity. The position and intensity of the band at 1642 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox indicate that it may be assigned to C=N stretching frequency. This band appears at 1630 cm^{-1} in the deuterated 5-nitro-rapox. Further, resacetophenone oxime (rapox) exhibits C=N stretching vibration at 1635 cm^{-1} . The band near 1630 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ may be attributed to asymmetric stretching of the nitro group. The OH in-plane bending seems to occur at 1530 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox. This is supported by the appearance of a new band at 1110 cm^{-1} in the deuterated 5-nitro-rapox. It is reported³ that the in-plane bending vibrations of associated OH frequently occurs as two absorption maxima in the region $1500\text{--}1300$ cm^{-1} . The deuterated 5-nitro-rapox has a shoulder near 1088 cm^{-1} corresponding to the band at 1490 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox. It is, therefore, reasonable to assign the band at 1490 cm^{-1} in 5-nitro-rapox to associated OH in-plane bending mode. The OH in-plane bending vibrations also occur near 1490 cm^{-1} in $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$. The symmetric stretching frequencies of $-\text{NO}_2$ group in 5-nitro-rapox, $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ appear at 1300 cm^{-1} , 1340 cm^{-1} and 1330 cm^{-1} respectively.

5-Nitro-rapox should have a stretching band due to the N-O vibration in =NOH group. The position and intensity of the band at 910 cm^{-1} appears to fit with its assignment to N-O stretching frequency. This is supported by the fact that this band is not found in the infrared spectra of resacetophenone and 5-nitro-resacetophenone and it occurs in the deuterated 5-nitro-rapox at 912 cm^{-1} . $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ also show a band at 910 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to N-O stretching mode.

The Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes reveal bands at 486 cm^{-1} and 471 cm^{-1} respectively, which are missing in the spectrum of the ligand. These bands may, therefore, be assigned to the M-N-vibration. However, they may have some degree of mixed character. The results of the present investigation indicate that $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ may be represented by a planar structure involving the formation of a six membered chelate ring through N and O donor atoms.

The X-ray powder patterns of $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ show that the two complexes are not isostructural. Considering that the diamagnetic $\text{Ni}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ is square planar, it may be concluded that $\text{Cu}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_2\text{O}_5)_2$ is octahedral or distorted octahedral.

References

- 1a. R. ROBINSON and R. C. SHAH, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1490.
- 1b. R. E. OMER and C. HAMILTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 59, 643.
- 2a. A. V. PAIGANKAR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, 44, 197.
- 2b. A. V. PAIGANKAR and B. C. HALDAR, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 47, 135.
3. K. NAKANISHI, 'Infrared Absorption Spectroscopy', Holden-Day, Inc., San Francisco, p. 31.